

TECHNICAL SCIENCES

MISUSE OF AI FOR CYBERATTACKS AND COUNTERMEASURES

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ABSTRACT

Artificial intelligence (AI) is becoming an increasingly important element of modern information systems. However, the growing power and availability of AI also pose serious threats in the form of cyberattacks. This article analyzes the problem of AI abuse for cyberattacks and examines strategies to counter these attacks in modern information systems. It explores the various types of cyberattacks that use AI, as well as the techniques that can be used to detect, prevention and response to them. Important aspects of data security and measures to ensure the protection of information are also discussed. This article is important for researchers, practitioners, and information security professionals who are interested in understanding and combating the use of AI for cyberattacks.

Keywords: Artificial Intelligence (AI), cyberattacks, TensorFlow, Keras, Rectified Linear Unit (ReLU), Adam Optimizer.

ENTRY

In today's world, where information technology is becoming increasingly important in our daily lives, cybersecurity is becoming one of the most important issues. This is especially true for artificial intelligence (AI), which is used in a variety of fields, including cybersecurity. On the one hand, AI can be used to improve security, such as detecting and countering cyberattacks. On the other hand, AI can be used by attackers to conduct cyberattacks, including phishing attacks, attacks on identity systems, and attacks on network infrastructure [1]. This article examines both aspects of the use of AI in cybersecurity and offers strategies to counter AI abuse in cyberattacks. AI has become an integral part of today's digital world, where it enables innovation and improvement in many fields, including medicine, finance, transportation, trade, and others. However, along with the growing role of AI comes new challenges and threats, including abuse for cyberattacks [2]. The misuse of artificial intelligence systems to carry out cyberattacks is becoming an increasingly relevant threat in today's digital world. Thanks to the rapid development of AI technologies, attackers are gaining new opportunities to create sophisticated and innovative attacks that can lead to serious consequences for information systems, enterprises, and users. This article is devoted to the analysis of the problem of AI abuse for cyberattacks and ways to counteract these attacks in modern information systems. The purpose of this study is to examine various aspects of this problem and highlight the importance of developing effective security measures to prevent and respond to such threats. Further research will focus on ways to counter these attacks, including technological and strategic aspects. The general consideration of this topic will contribute to the understanding of modern challenges in the field of cybersecurity and contribute to the development of new strategies and solutions for the effective protection of information systems in the context of the constant development of AI.

AI can be used to carry out various types of cyberattacks because of its ability to analyze vast

amounts of data, recognize deviations, and make decisions based on that analysis. In the future, the problem of phishing attacks using artificial intelligence will be considered

FORMULATION OF THE PROBLEM

Phishing is a type of cyberattack that aims to obtain sensitive information, such as passwords, personal data, or financial information, by manipulating a potential victim. These attacks typically use fake emails, text messages, or other communication channels to impersonate a trusted source, such as a bank, company, or individual, and convince the victim to provide theirs. Sensitive data. In 2020, researchers from Microsoft announced the discovery of a new type of phishing attack that used deep learning to improve the effectiveness of spam. These attacks differed from traditional phishing methods due to the use of neural networks to select personalized texts and patterns in emails, making them more difficult to detect by spam filters. AI plays a significant role in amplifying phishing attacks, providing attackers with a range of tools and capabilities to improve the effectiveness and success of attacks. Here are some of the techniques and features used to use AI in phishing:

- Personalized attacks. AI can be used to analyze large amounts of data about potential victims, including their online behavior, interests, social media, and more. Based on this analysis, personalized phishing messages can be created that will be more likely to be perceived by the victim.
- Automated content creation. AI can be used to automatically generate phishing messages containing authentic-looking text. The use of Natural Language Processing (NLP) technologies allows you to create messages that sound high-quality and natural.
- Analysis of results. AI can analyze the results of phishing campaigns, taking into account metrics such as the number of emails opened, the number of clicks on links, the number of sensitive data entered, etc. This allows attackers to refine their attacks based on the data they receive and increase their effectiveness.

- Imitation of human behavior. AI can mimic human behavior when interacting with victims, making phishing attacks even more sophisticated. For example, automated agents may interact with victims through emails or chatbots in an attempt to trick them into performing certain actions.

- Use of machine learning. Attackers can use machine learning to analyze user data and improve attack strategies. For example, machine learning algorithms can determine the optimal time to send phishing emails or select the most effective text templates.

The use of AI in phishing attacks can have significant consequences for users and organizations. If a phishing attack is successful, attackers can gain access to sensitive information such as passwords, credit card numbers, or corporate data. Phishing attacks can result in financial losses for users or organizations due to fraud, money theft, or exposure of financial information. Phishing attacks can be aimed at spreading malware, such as viruses, or various types of malware. Potentially inciting users to engage in unsafe activities, such as entering sensitive information or downloading malware.

Building a neural network for selecting personalized texts and templates for phishing attacks can include several stages.

Data collection and preparation. The first step is to collect a large enough database of phishing emails and legitimate emails. The data must be labeled so that the neural network can distinguish between them. It may also be useful to analyze the structure and content of emails to identify common patterns and features.

Building a neural network model. Various neural network architectures can be used to select personalized texts and templates, such as recurrent neural networks (RNNs), convolutional neural networks (CNNs). It is possible that a combination of these architectures will be used to achieve better performance.

Model training. After building the architecture of the model, you need to train it on the prepared data. The training process includes data transfer over the network and correction of model parameters depending on the results of predictions.

Evaluation and adjustment of the model. After training the model, you need to evaluate its performance on test data and adjust the settings to achieve better performance and avoid overfitting.

Using the model to generate phishing emails. Once the model is trained and set up, it can be used to generate new phishing emails. The model can use the context retrieved from the database to create personalized text messages that are as legitimate as possible.

Checking results and improvements. Once phishing emails are generated, they can be tested for effectiveness and suitability. The results can be used to further train the model and improve its performance.

Detecting phishing attacks, including sending fake emails, is a complex cybersecurity issue. Phishing attacks are usually based on social engineering, where attackers use the manipulation of people's psychological properties to obtain sensitive information or perform certain actions. Fake emails may contain invitations to open links or attachments that contain malware or that

are simply designed to intercept sensitive information. Attackers often seek to mimic legitimate emails from well-known companies or individuals. They can use logos, design styles, and language-consistent with the original to make emails as compelling as possible. A variety of approaches and techniques can be used to identify fake emails with fake logos.

You can use computer vision and image processing techniques to analyze the visual characteristics of emails, including logos. Possible approaches include the use of pattern recognition algorithms and sample comparison to detect anomalies in the form of logos. Fake logos may have differences in image metadata, such as file size, file format, date of creation, etc. Analyzing this metadata can help identify fake images. Neural networks can be used to detect anomalous patterns in logo images. This may involve using autoencoders or deep convolutional neural networks to detect incorrect details or mismatches with known logos. The system can check the source of the emails and compare it with the company's official sources, such as their websites or email addresses. This can help identify fake emails that come from unknown or suspicious sources.

Now let's look at the techniques that can be used to detect, prevent, and respond to phishing attacks, which are based on analyzing user behavior and using machine learning to detect phishing messages.

Data collection. Collect data about user behavior, such as browsing history, frequency and characteristics of e-mails, response to suspicious messages, etc.

Data preprocessing. Process and clean the collected data for use in the analysis. This may include removing anomalous or incomplete records, as well as converting the data to an appropriate format for future reference.

Machine learning model development. Train a machine learning model on prepared data to detect phishing messages. A variety of classification algorithms can be used, such as the Bayesian classifier, the support vector method, or neural networks.

Integration of a user behavior analysis system. Develop a system that analyzes user behavior in real time, taking into account factors such as response times to messages, browsing suspicious websites, etc.

Risk assessment. Develop a risk assessment system that takes into account the results of user behavior analysis and detection of phishing messages. For example, you can use risk analysis techniques to assign a risk level to each user action.

Decision-making and security measures. Develop a system that, based on the risk assessment, takes appropriate security measures, such as blocking suspicious messages or forcing user authentication.

Testing and tuning. Conduct compliance and efficiency testing of the system, as well as adjust the parameters of machine learning models and algorithms for analyzing user behavior for optimal performance.

Continuous improvement. Continuously improve the system, taking into account new attack methods and updates in the field of machine learning and user behavior analysis.

The author proposes to apply this strategy for effective protection, using the example of code that uses

TensorFlow and Keras to create a machine learning model to classify emails as legitimate or phishing:

```
import tensorflow as tf
from tensorflow.keras.models import Sequential
from tensorflow.keras.layers import Dense
from sklearn.model_selection import train_test_split
import pandas as pd

# Load the dataset
data = pd.read_csv('emails.csv')
# Preprocess the data
# This step will vary depending on your dataset
# You might want to normalize numerical features, or do some feature engineering
X = preprocess_features(data)
y = preprocess_labels(data)
# Split the data into training and test sets
X_train, X_test, y_train, y_test = train_test_split(X, y, test_size=0.2, random_state=42)
# Define the model
model = Sequential([
    Dense(32, activation='relu', input_shape=(X_train.shape[1],)),
    Dense(32, activation='relu'),
    Dense(1, activation='sigmoid'),
])
# Compile the model
model.compile(
    optimizer='adam',
    loss='binary_crossentropy',
    metrics=['accuracy'],
)
# Train the model
model.fit(
    X_train,
    y_train,
    validation_data=(X_test, y_test),
    epochs=10,
    batch_size=32,
)
```

This code creates a neural network with two hidden layers that use ReLU as an activation function and one output layer that uses a sigmoid as an activation function for binary classification [3]. The model is trained using the Adam optimizer and binary cross-entropy as a loss function [4]. It should be noted that this is only a general strategy, in practice it will be necessary to adapt this code to a specific dataset, including processing the data and choosing the right characteristics to use as inputs to the model.

ReLU, or Rectified Linear Unit, is an activation function used in neural networks. It is determined by the following mathematical formula: $f(x) = \max(0, x)$

This function returns 0 if the input value is less than or equal to 0 and returns the input value if it is greater than 0 [5]. ReLU is used in this strategy because it adds the necessary nonlinearity to the model without complicating computations, as can be the case with other activation functions such as sigmoid or hyperbolic tangent [6].

The model, which is trained using the Adam optimizer and binary cross-entropy as a function of loss,

works on the principles of deep learning. The Adam optimizer is used to update the model weights in order to minimize the loss function. Adam is a stochastic optimization method that takes into account both the first moment (mean) of gradients and the second moment (uncorrelated variance) of gradients. This helps the model to match faster and find the optimal weights. Binary cross-entropy is used as a loss function for binary classification models, where the output can be labels 0 or 1 [7]. This loss function measures the distance between the true labels and the predictions of the model. The more the predictions of the models differ from the true labels, the greater the loss. During the learning process, the model first makes predictions based on current weights, then measures the loss using binary cross-entropy. It then uses the Adam optimizer to update the model's weights in a way that minimizes loss. The Adam Optimizer is a stochastic optimization method that uses the first (mean) and second (uncorrelated variance) moments of gradients. The scales are updated according to the formula:

$$m_t = \beta_1 * m_{t-1} + (1 - \beta_1) * g_t$$

$$v_t = \beta_2 * v_{t-1} + (1 - \beta_2) * g_t^2$$

$$m_{hat} = \frac{m_t}{1 - \beta_1^t}$$

$$v_{hat} = \frac{v_t}{1 - \beta_2^t}$$

$$\theta_t = \theta_{t-1} - \frac{\alpha * m_{hat}}{sqrt(v_{hat} + \epsilon)}$$

Where m_t and v_t are the estimates of the first and second moments of the gradients, respectively, g_t is the gradient at the current step, θ_t are the weights of the model at the current step, α is the learning rate, and $\beta_1, \beta_2, \epsilon$ are the hyperparameters that control the weight of the moment scores, m_{hat} is the additional term for stabilization.

Binary cross-entropy is a loss function that measures the distance between the true labels and predictions of a model. It is determined by the formula:

$$L(y, \hat{y}) = -\frac{1}{N} * \sum [y * \log(\hat{y}) + (1 - y) * \log(1 - \hat{y})]$$

Where y are the true labels, $\hat{y}$ are the predictions of the model, and N are the number of examples in the data.

Various techniques can be used to improve the machine learning model, which uses the Adam optimizer and binary cross-entropy as a loss function. Here are some math concepts that can be used:

Regularization is a method that adds a penalty to the loss function to prevent overtraining. This can be L1 regularization (which leads to sparse patterns) or L2 regularization (which penalizes large weights). Regularization is added to the loss function as follows:

$$L'(y, \hat{y}) = L(y, \hat{y}) + \lambda * R(w)$$

Where $L'(y, \hat{y})$ is the new loss function, $L(y, \hat{y})$ is the original loss function, λ is the regularization parameter, and $R(w)$ is the regularization function.

is the regularization term (for example, for L1 regularization or for L2 regularization), is the model weight. $L(y, \hat{y}) + \lambda R(w) + \beta_1 \|w\|_1 + \beta_2 \|w\|_2^2$

Hyperparameter optimization is the process of tuning model parameters that are not learned in the learning process. For the Adam optimizer, this can be the learning rate, and. This can be done using a variety of methods, such as grid search, random search, or optimization using gradients (e.g., gradient descent).

Early stopping is a method that terminates learning when the quality on the validation kit stops improving. This helps prevent overtraining.

Model ensembles are a method that combines predictions from multiple models. This can be implemented through a variety of methods, such as majority voting, boosting, or bagging. Ensembles usually improve the stability and accuracy of models.

Conclusion. The use of artificial intelligence in cybersecurity is becoming increasingly relevant, especially in the context of countering phishing attacks. Artificial intelligence can help automate the process of detecting phishing attacks, but it cannot replace basic security measures such as secure coding and user education. Using machine learning to analyze user behavior and identify unusual patterns can be an effective means of detecting phishing attacks. However, it also requires a lot of data and resources to train and tune the models. Secure encoding, such as clearing sensitive data when it is no longer needed, is also an essential element of protection against phishing attacks. This can help mitigate potential losses if a phishing attack does successfully compromise a user's session. Overall, artificial intelligence and machine learning can play an important role in countering phishing attacks. However, they must be used in combination with other security methods, including secure coding and user education. It's important to remember that no matter how effective AI technologies are, they can't replace the human factor. Educating users about potential phishing risks and how to avoid them is an important part of your overall

protection strategy. It's also worth noting that the use of AI in cybersecurity requires constant updating and improvement, as attackers are constantly developing new attack methods. Therefore, it is important not only to develop new protection technologies, but also to constantly improve existing ones. Finally, it's important to remember that AI is just a tool, and its effectiveness largely depends on how it's used. Developers must be careful to use AI responsibly, taking into account user privacy and ethical concerns.

References

1. Buczak, A. L., & Guven, E. (2016). A survey of data mining and machine learning methods for cyber security intrusion detection. *IEEE Communications Surveys & Tutorials*, 18(2), 1153-1176.
2. Barreno, M., Nelson, B., Sears, R., Joseph, A. D., & Tygar, J. D. (2010). Can machine learning be secure?. *ACM Transactions on Information and System Security (TISSEC)*, 13(4), 1-36.
3. Aurelien Geron (2023). *Hands-On Machine Learning with Scikit-Learn, Keras, and TensorFlow: Concepts, Tools, and Techniques to Build Intelligent Systems* 3rd Edition, 850
4. Diederik P. Kingma, Jimmy Ba "Adam: A Method for Stochastic Optimization", this is the original article that introduced the Adam optimizer.
5. Ian Goodfellow, Yoshua Bengio, Aaron Courville (2016). *Deep Learning (Adaptive Computation and Machine Learning series)*, 800
6. Xavier Glorot, Yoshua Bengio "Understanding the difficulty of training deep feedforward neural networks", this article contains information about the problems that the Adam optimizer solves.
7. Kevin P. Murphy (2022). *Probabilistic Machine Learning: An Introduction (Adaptive Computation and Machine Learning series)*, 864